

Investing in Talent Management to Enhance Marketing Innovation: A Case Study of Asiacell Company, Kirkuk Branch

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Abstract

The research aims to explore the potential of enhancing marketing innovation through its dimensions, namely (technological capabilities, research and development, and marketing activities), by relying on investment in talent management according to its dimensions (talent attraction, talent development, and talent retention). Asiacell's Kirkuk branch was chosen as the research field, being one of the leading telecommunications companies in Iraq. A checklist was used as a data collection tool from employees at the Kirkuk branch and analyzed based on the sub-variables and at the overall level to extract results. These results were analyzed using a set of statistical and mathematical methods and equations to reach conclusions. One of the most significant findings was that investment in talent management leads to enhancing marketing innovation, which contributes to improving the capabilities and skills of the company's employees under study. Based on these conclusions, several recommendations were proposed, the most important of which is that the company should seriously consider establishing a dedicated talent management center to attract, nurture, and provide all necessary resources and support to develop and grow their talents, particularly in the area of marketing innovation for the company's telecommunications and other services.

Keywords: *Talent Management, Marketing Innovation, Talent Development, Technological Capabilities, Asiacell Telecommunications Company.*

JEL Classification codes: *M31, J53*

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Introduction

Marketing innovation is considered one of the leading requirements in the telecommunications field in our modern era, which has witnessed a massive revolution that has become difficult for researchers and scholars to fully comprehend due to its rapid changes. This necessitates finding ways and methods to keep up with and adapt to these changes, thereby effectively investing in and managing talents to navigate this vast field and innovate feasible and novel approaches within it.

Through their field visits to the company under study, the researchers found that the methods employed by the company to market its products are traditional and do not rise to a level that enables them to reach global standards or keep pace with the rapid developments in the telecommunications sector worldwide.

The research problem can be formulated through the following questions:

1. Does the company rely on innovative and modern methods in marketing its products and providing its services?
2. How can the company under study invest in talent management?
3. What are the methods that enable talent management to enhance marketing innovation within the company under study?

Importance of Research

The importance of this research can be summarized as follows:

1. This research serves as a scientific reference that benefits researchers in the fields of talent management and marketing innovation for organizations operating in the market.
2. It contributes to improving the investment in talent management within our companies and preparing them to enhance marketing through innovation, utilizing the latest technologies and advanced scientific methods in this area.
3. Both service and industrial organizations can rely on the concepts presented in this research to develop, improve, and enhance business operations.

Research Objectives

The research aims to:

1. Provide a clear and specific understanding of the concepts of talent management and marketing innovation for the company under study.
2. Clarify the potential for investing in talent management to scientifically and technically enhance marketing innovation at Asiacell / Kirkuk.
3. Identify the current state of talent investment mechanisms at Asiacell / Kirkuk.
4. Present a clear and detailed overview of the services offered by the company under study, its ability to compete in the local market, and the potential to improve the competitiveness of its products to reach a global level.

Hypothetical Framework of Research

The research's hypothetical framework can be outlined to demonstrate that utilizing the dimensions of talent management—namely (talent attraction, talent development, and talent retention)—can enhance the company's marketing innovation, represented by (technological capabilities, research and development, and marketing activities).

Figure 1. Hypothetical Framework of Research

Source: Prepared by the researchers

Research Hypothesis

The research relies on the following hypothesis:

Investing in the dimensions of talent management, represented by (talent attraction, talent development, and talent retention), leads to enhancing marketing innovation within the company under study by focusing on the dimensions of marketing innovation, which include (technological capabilities, research and development, and marketing activities). The goal is to invest in talent management through its strategies, policies, and activities to achieve innovative methods and approaches in marketing.

Methodology

The research adopted the case study methodology, which is characterized by its ability to analyze the phenomenon under investigation in a detailed and realistic manner. This was done through reviewing, observing, and following the sequence of production processes, conducting field visits, and personal interviews with relevant employees. Additionally, a checklist was used to collect the necessary data and information for the research, which were then analyzed to extract the required results.

Data and Information Collection Methods

The following methods were used to gather the necessary data and information for the research:

1. For the theoretical aspect, the research relied on information available in scientific references such as books, journals, articles, and theses related to the research topic, which were accessible in libraries that the researchers reviewed, in addition to utilizing the World Wide Web.
2. As for the analytical framework of the research, it was based on the following:
 - a. Field visits made by the researchers to Asiatic / Kirkuk during the preparation of the research to observe and examine closely the marketing services and all aspects related to the main and sub-variables of the research, and to evaluate the applicability of concepts related to these variables.

b. Personal interviews conducted with a sample of 25 employees from the company, selected from managers and some experienced staff involved in service operations, marketing, research and development, and design. They were provided with checklists to answer the questions related to the research.

c. Checklist: A checklist was designed for each sub-variable of the two main variables—talent management (comprising talent attraction, talent development, and talent retention) and its impact on enhancing marketing innovation for the company under study, focusing on the dimensions of marketing innovation (technological capabilities, research and development, and marketing activities).

The researchers designed the items in these checklists based on the sources referenced in the theoretical section of the research. The items were then reviewed by a group of experts from the University of Kirkuk and the University of Al-Hadba, and the items were revised to better serve the scientific research. The checklist included a three-point scale, assigning a weight of 10 for "completely matching," 5 for "partially matching," and 0 for "not matching."

The researchers performed statistical analysis to derive the results by using the following statistical methods: (Dawy, 2010: 169; Jowad, 2015: 226; Al-Lami & Jowad, 2014: 56).

Results

Calculation Formulae

$$\text{Result} = \text{Weights} \times \text{Frequencies} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Average} = \text{Total Result} \div \text{Total Frequencies} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Percentage of Compliance} = \text{Average} \div 10 \text{ (the highest weight in the scale)} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Hypothetical Mean} = \text{Percentage of Compliance} \times \text{Average} \div \text{Total Result} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Gap Size} = 1 - \text{Percentage of Compliance} \quad (5)$$

A grading scale was used to evaluate the responses for each variable based on its compliance in the studied company, as follows:

- Excellent: 100 - 90
- Very Good: 89 - 80
- Good: 79 - 70
- Average: 69 - 60
- Acceptable: 59 - 50
- Not Available: 1 – 49

Literature Review

The Concept of Talent Management

Cappelli and Keller (2014, p. 331) define talent management as a set of established practices aimed at placing the right person in the right job at the right time. Meyers and van Woerkom (2014, p. 192) define talent management as "the systematic use of human resource management activities to attract, identify, develop, and retain individuals considered 'talented.'" Abdullah and Abubakar (2017, p. 36) describe talent management as a process of attracting, retaining, disseminating, and developing high-potential individuals who possess specific qualities valued by the organization. Ibrahim and AlOmari (2020, p. 1296) describe talent management as a concept encompassing a set of activities related to attracting, selecting, developing, and retaining talented employees in an organizational context strategically. Chen et al. (2021, p. 428) define talent management as organizational activities aimed at attracting, selecting, developing, and retaining talented employees.

Importance of Talent Management

Alzuod (2024, p. 73) indicates that the primary purpose of talent management is to enhance employees' abilities and demonstrate high performance, aligning them with the organization's strategic directions to ensure its survival and growth.

Talent management is a critical competitive advantage for modern businesses and the foundational element for their development and prosperity. Due to the global economic expansion, many organizations have turned to focus on talent management to address challenges. The importance of talent management lies in the following (Siti, 2020, p. 132):

1. It is an essential complement to attract skilled employees to work in the organization.
2. Talent management ensures the ability to achieve success and retain the necessary talent.
3. Talent management represents one of the most valuable resources for any organization.
4. Talent management is a critical success factor for organizations.
5. Focusing on talent management contributes to achieving higher performance levels.

Dimensions of Talent Management

1. Attracting Talent:

Ata (2022, p. 93) states that organizations face significant challenges when it comes to attracting talented individuals to fill key vacant positions and selecting the best among them. For attraction to be successful, organizations must follow a successful strategy that includes ethical practices at every stage of the recruitment process, relying on a strong market reputation that allows them to withstand intense competition, also known as the "war for talent." Chuai (2008, p. 20) defines it as the process of attracting high-performing individuals based on specific characteristics and requirements that align with the vacant position.

2. Developing Talent:

Talent development plays a crucial role in organizations by enhancing human capital and cultivating the leaders necessary for competitiveness (Al Mannai et al., 2017, p. 4). Noura and Khadija (2022, p. 9) explain that talent development means enhancing the ability of talented individuals to cope with changes in the surrounding environment and successfully meet both their needs and those of the organization they work for. Development is a vital element in the professional life of talented employees within the organization. It must include the development of knowledge, behaviors, and skills, achieved through: strengthening and advancing their talents, participation in goals and new tasks to acquire skills that improve performance, providing growth opportunities aligned with the

skills required for development, participation in training programs, the ability to implement new ideas, and tackling emerging work-related issues.

3. Retaining Talent:

Salhi (2020, p. 165) notes that talented employees are similar to frogs in a pond: they can jump out whenever they wish. Similarly, an organization can focus on ensuring that the workforce remains within the institution or try to retain employees by offering incentives. In other words, current leaders can create an environment and incentives that encourage talented employees to stay in the organization and prevent them from leaving. This may include providing non-financial rewards or relying on legal means such as employment contracts that prevent employees from leaving the organization.

Marketing Innovation

Concept of Marketing Innovation

Qandeel (2010, p. 138) defines a marketing innovator as "someone who has the desire and ability to come up with new and unconventional ideas, and who has the ability to apply these ideas—at least to some extent—or contribute to turning them into practical marketing practices within the organization." Therefore, having the ability to innovate in the marketing field may not be enough for a person to be considered an innovator; this ability must also be accompanied by the desire to innovate. Ja'four (2016, p. 5) further elaborates that marketing innovation is the process of implementing new and unconventional ideas into actual marketing practices.

Elements of Marketing Innovation

Technological Capabilities

Suleiman and Ahmed (2021, p. 13) state that both innovation and invention create new added value and contribute significantly to the organization's share of that value. Technological capabilities play a vital role in the growth of companies by introducing new products and services. Thus, technology and innovation are crucial in creating a competitive advantage.

Research and Development (R&D)

Shoib (2014, p. 6) emphasizes that research and development activities have gained significant importance, particularly in relation to technological advancements, as they represent a means of expanding technological knowledge that drives innovation. This, in turn, suggests an increase in the return on investments, both material and human.

Marketing Activities

The marketing activities conducted by an organization generally help the organization achieve excellence. Marketing management is responsible for planning, organizing, directing, and controlling marketing activities to ensure that exchange processes occur efficiently and effectively to meet the goals of all involved parties (Abu Alifla, 2003, p. 49). The importance of marketing activities in marketing innovation lies in introducing new products or making significant improvements to existing products, which help customers distinguish between products from competing organizations. Additionally, marketing activities primarily aim at marketing innovation through these products, and by studying the needs and desires of customers, which plays a decisive role in the marketing process (Moreira et al., 2012, p. 199).

Results and Discussion

Talent Management

1. Attracting Talent

Table 1 presents the checklist for the sub-variable of attracting talent. It shows that items (2 and 5) received the highest weight, totaling (20) exact matches out of (60) total weight, which corresponds to (33.3%). This percentage exceeds the hypothetical mean of (11%), indicating that the company has a strategic approach through its vision, mission, and clear strategies that align with environmental changes concerning attracting talent. These strategies include both material and moral incentives.

Meanwhile, the remaining items achieved (20) total weight, corresponding to (33.3%), which is also higher than the hypothetical mean. This indicates that the organization has the ability to identify gaps in acquiring talent, relying on human resource management planning processes to determine the shortage of required talent. Additionally, transparency and fairness in clarifying career paths were followed.

The overall average was (66.6%) out of (10), with a gap size of (33.4%) from the ideal reality expected to be achieved by this research, placing the results at a "Medium" level. This outcome reinforces the validity of the research hypothesis concerning the "Attracting Talent" dimension of Talent Management.

Table 1. Checklist for the "Attracting Talent" Dimension

S	Attracting Talent	Completely Matched	Partially Matched	Not Matched
1	The company plans systematically to determine current and future talent needs.		√	
2	The company has a clear strategy to attract talent using an innovative methodology and modern methods.	√		
3	The organization relies on a clear plan to attract talented employees to sensitive and high-priority positions within the organization.		√	
4	The organization is characterized by transparency in decision-making, which helps attract the largest number of talents.		√	
5	The salary structure, bonuses, and material incentives based on the organization's level contribute to attracting talent to work there.	√		
6	The organization's management flexibility between superiors and subordinates helps attract a large number of talents.		√	
	Weights	10	5	0
	Frequency	2	4	0
	Result	20	20	0
	Average	6.66		
	Percentage of Match	0.666		
	Hypothetical Mean	0.11		
	Gap Size	0.334		

2. Talent Development

Table 2 shows the checklist for the talent development dimension, where it is clear that paragraphs (1, 4, 6) received the highest weight, totaling (30) out of (60), which is (50%) higher than the

theoretical mean of (12.5%). This indicates that the company is developing its employees by allocating the necessary budget for development. The company also applies the policy of placing the right person in the right position and providing opportunities for talented individuals to manage positions in senior and middle management. Additionally, the company follows a job rotation policy to fill vacancies with talented individuals.

Meanwhile, the remaining paragraphs received a total of (15) weight, or (25%), which is also higher than the theoretical mean, indicating the need for the company to foster a spirit of competition, identify and develop undiscovered talents, and raise awareness among employees about the importance of receiving proper training that leads to the development of their talents.

The overall average was (7.5) out of (10), which corresponds to (75%) at a "Good" level, and the gap size was (25%) from the desired reality of the research, which supports the validity of the research hypothesis regarding the talent development dimension within the talent management framework applied in the study.

Table 2. The Checklist for the Talent Development Dimension

S	Talent Development	Completely Compliant	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant
1	The organization allocates a special budget for the development of the best and most skilled employees.	√		
2	The organization seeks to foster a spirit of competition among employees to enhance their performance and talent.		√	
3	The organization provides training opportunities for various employees with the aim of discovering new talents and developing existing ones.		√	
4	The management of the organization provides opportunities for talented individuals to manage senior positions within the company.	√		
5	The organization encourages newly hired talented employees to undergo training and guidance.		√	
6	The company implements job rotation policies to empower employees.	√		
	Weights	10	5	0
	Frequency	3	3	0
	Result	30	15	0
	Average	7.5		
	Percentage of Compliance	0.75		
	Hypothetical Mean	0.125		
	Gap Size	0.25		

3. Retaining Talent

Table 3 shows the checklist for the dimension of talent retention. It indicates that items (1, 2, and 6) received the highest weight, totaling (30) out of (60), which represents (50%), higher than the hypothetical average of (12.5%). This indicates that the company places great importance on both personal and professional development of its employees, and provides an organizational climate conducive to encouraging employees in innovation and generating new ideas. Additionally, the company develops its employees by identifying their training needs and preparing suitable training programs to achieve the company's strategies and goals. Meanwhile, the remaining items received a total weight of (15), or (25%), which is also higher than the hypothetical average of (12.5%). This suggests that the company needs to create favorable conditions for retaining talent, study the labor

market, and monitor the actions of competing companies regarding employee retention, such as incentives and wages, which should match or exceed those of competitors. The overall average was (7.5) out of (10), or (75%), at a "Good" level, with a gap size of (25%), confirming the validity of the hypothesis regarding this dimension of talent management.

Table 3. Checklist for Talent Retention Dimension

S	Retention of Talent	Completely Compliant	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant
1	The organization is concerned with the personal and professional development of its various professional employees.	√		
2	The organization works to provide an appropriate work environment that leads to innovation, creativity, and updating work patterns.	√		
3	The economic importance and position of the organization necessitate providing the right and suitable conditions to retain its talents.		√	
4	The organization treats its employees as partners rather than workers, especially in setting and implementing goals.		√	
5	The organization relies on an incentive system to retain its talented individuals.		√	
6	The organization organizes training and development programs for its talents to enhance and improve their performance.	√		
	Weights	10	5	0
	Frequency	3	3	0
	Result	30	15	0
	Average	7.5		
	Percentage of Compliance	0.75		
	Hypothetical Mean	0.125		
	Gap Size	0.25		

Marketing Innovation

1. Technological Capabilities

Table 4 shows that the items (1, 3, 6) received the highest weight, totaling (30) out of (60), representing (50%), which is higher than the hypothesized mean of (12.5%). This indicates that the organization is striving to acquire the technological means that will help achieve a competitive advantage for its business processes. The company is also aiming to obtain technological capabilities that establish an integrated technological infrastructure capable of facing external environmental risks and threats. Meanwhile, the remaining items received a total weight of (15) out of (60), representing (25%), which is also higher than the hypothesized mean. This requires the company to follow appropriate steps to encourage its employees to develop technologies for product innovation or renewal, as well as to identify and adopt competitive technologies. The overall score for this dimension was (7.5) out of (10), indicating a (Good) level, with a gap size of (25%), confirming the validity of the research hypothesis for this aspect of marketing innovation.

Table 4. The Inspection List for the Technological Capabilities Dimension.

S	Technological Capabilities	Completely Compliant	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant
1	The company's management relies on the latest technological means that help reduce delivery times.	√		
2	The company's management encourages the development of technological applications for the products it offers.		√	
3	The company focuses on the different types of technology components used, as they play a crucial role in building its technological capabilities.	√		
4	Technological changes significantly impact the creation of substantial marketing opportunities in the product sector.		√	
5	The organization allocates a high budget to invest in modern technological means.		√	
6	The company monitors technological developments owned by its competing companies.	√		
	Weights	10	5	0
	Frequency	3	3	0
	Result	30	15	0
	Mean	7.5		
	Percentage of Compliance	0.75		
	Hypothetical Average Rate	0.125		
	Gap Size	0.25		

2. Research and Development

Table 5 shows the checklist for the research and development aspect of competitive innovation. Items (1, 2, and 4) received the highest weight, totaling (30) out of (60), or (50%), which is higher than the hypothetical average of (12.5%). This confirms that the company is focused on developing the means by which it delivers products, establishing strategies to ensure it acquires strategic capabilities and core competencies capable of satisfying customers and meeting their current and future needs and desires. Furthermore, it is working to acquire the latest technologies or innovate technologies that provide a competitive edge.

On the other hand, the remaining items received (15) total weight, which is also above the hypothetical average, at (25%). This indicates that the company must pay attention to research and development activities that reduce waste and thus lower costs. Additionally, the company should increase its focus on employees and invest in their latent energy and tacit knowledge.

The overall mean is (0.5) out of (10), representing (75%) with a "Good" level, and the gap size is (25%) from the desired reality as expected by the researchers. This supports the validity of the hypothesis related to the research and development aspect of competitive innovation.

Table 5. Checklist for Research and Development Aspect

S	Research and Development Aspect	Completely Compliant	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant
1	The management of our company seeks to develop its products by improving service delivery methods through the use of modern technologies.	√		
2	The management of the organization strives to acquire strategic capabilities and core competencies	√		

	that provide a deep understanding of the current and future needs of customers.			
3	Our organization is committed to investing in research and development activities to reduce costs.		√	
4	Our company invests in new means of research and development to gain a competitive advantage.	√		
5	The organization ensures the utilization of the creative capabilities of its employees.		√	
6	Our company follows a scientific methodology in finding innovative solutions to the problems it faces.		√	
	Weights	10	5	0
	Frequency	3	3	0
	Result	30	15	0
	Average	7.5		
	Percentage of Compliance	0.75		
	Average Hypothetical Value	0.125		
	Gap Size	0.25		

3. Flexibility

Table 6 refers to the checklist for the marketing activities dimension of marketing innovation. The first two items (1, 2) received the highest weight, totaling (20) out of (60), or (33.3%), which is higher than the hypothetical average of (0.11). This indicates that the company involves its employees in the marketing process to apply feasible new ideas related to introducing improvements in internal marketing activities and adopting agile marketing practices by reducing waste and avoiding high inventory.

The remaining items also received a total weight of (20) out of (60), or (33.3%), indicating the necessity for the company to have a modern marketing communication system capable of accomplishing marketing activities in line with advancements in communication, information technology, and the requirements of electronic marketing, which makes time and space values equal to zero.

The overall average for this dimension is (6.666) out of (10), or (66.6%), with a gap size of (33.4%) from the desired reality, reflecting a moderate level. This confirms the validity of the research hypothesis for the marketing activities dimension of marketing innovation.

Table 6. Checklist for the Marketing Activities Dimension of Marketing Innovation

S	Marketing Activities	Completely Compliant	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant
1	The company constantly seeks to introduce improvements in its internal marketing activities to reduce high inventory.	√		
2	The company's management involves those responsible for the marketing process in activities aimed at improving the performance of the tasks they carry out.	√		
3	The company relies on an integrated system that combines modern technological systems with marketing activities to minimize errors.		√	
4	The use of a modern marketing communication system contributes to completing the company's marketing activities and monitoring competitors' activities.		√	
5	Our company works on introducing new products that help customers distinguish between the products of competing companies.		√	
6	Our company studies customer needs and desires, which play a decisive role in the marketing process.		√	

Weights	10	5	0
Frequency	2	4	0
Result	20	20	0
Average	6.666		
Percentage of Agreement	0.666		
Hypothetical Mean	0.11		
Gap Size	0.334		

Analysis of Checklists at the Overall Level

To understand the overall analysis of the checklists for the sub-variables of the two main variables (Talent Management and Marketing Innovation), and to determine the ability of talent management investment in enhancing the company's marketing innovation, Table 7 shows the analysis of the results and checklists at the overall level. It includes a comparison between the variables, their compliance percentage, and the gap size between the variables individually and collectively, as follows:

1. The overall average compliance rate for the talent management of the company under study was (72.2%) at a "Good" level with a gap size of (27.8%) from the desired reality, and the compliance percentage for the talent management dimensions individually was (0.75, 0.75, 0.75, 0.66) respectively, according to the virtual research framework.
2. The overall average compliance rate for the concurrent engineering of the competitive positioning variable in the factory was (72.2%) at a "Good" level, with a gap size of (27.8%) from the desired reality. The compliance percentage for the marketing innovation dimensions individually was (0.75, 0.66, 0.75, 0.75), respectively, according to their order in the virtual research framework.
3. The overall compliance index for the two main research variables was (72.2%) at a "Good" level, with a gap size of (27.8%) from the desired reality, which was derived by averaging the overall compliance rate for the two main research variables. This confirms the validity of the research hypothesis, which states that the effective and realistic investment in talent management through its sub-dimensions (Attracting Talent, Talent Development, Talent Retention) will enhance marketing innovation for the company in the market, through its dimensions (Technological Capabilities, Research and Development, Marketing Activities).

Table 7. Analysis of Checklist Results at the Overall Level

Talent Management			Competitive Innovation		
Dimensions	Percentage of Compliance	Gap Size	Dimensions	Percentage of Compliance	Gap Size
Attracting Talent	0.666	0.334	Technological Capabilities	0.75	0.25
Talent Development	0.75	0.25	Research and Development	0.75	0.25
Talent Retention	0.75	0.25	Marketing Activities	0.666	0.334
Overall Average	0.722	0.278	Overall Average	0.722	0.278
Overall Index	0.722	0.278			

Conclusion

Upon reviewing the service operations in the company, it was found that the company's management pays little attention to talent management and suffers from a lack of adherence to the elements of competitive marketing innovation. This issue is evident between product design processes, operations, and other production stages.

It was revealed from the checklists of the talent management dimensions that there is some alignment between these dimensions in terms of compliance rates and the gap size compared to the desired reality in the research. This has, in turn, reflected on the dimensions of competitive innovation in a similar manner, indicating that there is a relationship and alignment between the two main variables of the research.

The overall average of the two main variables (talent management) aligns in terms of compliance rates and gap sizes, which indicates harmony and compatibility between the two variables. This demonstrates that the application of talent management within the company can support the implementation of competitive marketing innovation.

Recommendations

The company management should pay increasing and continuous attention to the dimensions of talent management by relying on the latest strategies, policies, and practices used in human resource management related to talent management.

It is essential to motivate talented employees and encourage them to innovate and creatively develop services in a continuously evolving and sustainable manner.

The company should establish developmental and training programs for employees both inside and outside the company, involving employees in external training courses focused on developing their talents and skills in improving the methods and processes used to deliver products and services.

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